

Development and Improvement of the National Tourism Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract:

This paper examines the role of national standards in the development of the tourism industry, their impact on the quality of services, increasing competitiveness and forming a positive image of the country. Paper explains the process of standard development and implementation, as well as analyzes the existing standardization system in the field of tourism. The author suggests measures to improve national standards based on the results of the study.

Keywords: quality of services, competitiveness, standard, certification, efficiency.

Introduction

Standards are an integral part of the tourism industry, as they help to ensure that tourists have a consistent and reliable experience no matter where they are going. Standards provide the foundation for best practices in all aspects of the tourism industry, from the quality of accommodation to the safety of transportation.

The importance of standards in tourism and hotel business is high, as they give consumers an idea of the quality, safety, and consistency. Implementation and use of standards ensures that a tourism enterprise provides high-quality services that meet all the needs of customers. Standards may include recommendations on health and safety practices, service quality, environmental sustainability, accessibility, food safety, and customer feedback.

Methodology

Since 2016, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been taking significant steps to develop its tourism industry and improve the quality of services provided to tourists. In 2018, the State Committee for Tourism Development of Uzbekistan developed the "Concept for the Development of the Tourism Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan" for the period 2019-2025, which includes measures to

improve tourism infrastructure, develop new tourist routes and destinations, and enhance service quality. The country has launched a number of initiatives aimed at training professionals in the tourism sector and raising customer service standards.

Additionally, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has developed a national Tourism Development Strategy until 2030. The strategy includes the use and development of a cluster approach, which is an advanced and effective mechanism for concentrating efforts of both government bodies and private entrepreneurial initiatives in creating tourism infrastructure.

Analyses

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of standards is carried out by a group of specialists from the State Unitary Enterprise "Tourist Services Certification Center" within the Technical Committee. The organization is responsible for ensuring that tourist enterprises comply with general standards. Enterprises that have passed the mandatory inspection receive certificates and licenses. When the need for a standard is established, experts develop, discuss, and coordinate the standard project. The coordination of work on the development of standards is carried out by the Secretariat of the Technical Committee. The Center serves as the Secretariat of the Technical Committee on Tourism Standardization. Standard projects undergo examination at the Agency "Uzstandard" and are put into effect by the resolution of the Agency "Uzstandard."

Compliance with national standards, developed by the State Unitary Enterprise "Tourist Services Certification Center", allows tourist enterprises to operate freely in the Republic of Uzbekistan and meet the needs of consumers. Compliance with national standards in this regard also serves as a kind of quality guarantee for both domestic tourists - citizens of our country traveling to cities of the Republic or wishing to travel abroad, and for international tourists visiting our country for leisure, recreation, visiting relatives, exploring historical sites and monuments. The presence of a certificate of conformity for the servicing enterprise means that tourists can be assured that the organization meets all the stated requirements of the standard, and therefore, there is a high probability that the tourist will be satisfied with the quality of the services provided.

Results

Currently, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are 31 national standards in place to regulate the tourism industry. Among them, in 2024, the following standards were adopted: UzMSt 125:2024 "Tourist services. Accommodation facilities. Classification point system", UzMSt 189:2024 "Tourist services. Modular hotels. Classification system", and UzMSt 190:2024 "Tourist services. Glamping and yurts. Classification system."

Some of the national standards regulating the tourism industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan are identical to the international ISO standards. These standards are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Identical national and international standards

№	Национальный стандарт	Международный стандарт
1	O'z DSt ISO 18513:2017 "Tourist services. Hotels and other types of tourist accommodation facilities. Terminology"	ISO 18513:2003 "Tourism services – Hotels and other types of tourism accommodation – Terminology"
2	O'Z DSt ISO 14785:2018 "Tourist Information Bureaus. Tourist information and reception services. Requirements"	ISO 14785:2014 "Tourist information offices - Tourist information and reception services – Requirements"
3	O'Z DSt ISO 13009:2019 "Tourist services. Requirements and recommendations for the activities of	ISO 13009:2015 "Tourism and related services - Requirements and recommendations for beach operation"

	the beach”	
4	O'Z DSt ISO18065: 2019 “Tourist services. Tourist services provided in specially protected natural areas. Requirements”	ISO 18065:2015 “Tourism and related services — Tourist services for public use provided by Natural Protected Areas Authorities — Requirements”

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of research materials

In the process of research, it was also found that when creating some tourism standards in the Republic of Uzbekistan, similar ISO standards were used, including general requirements for various types of tourism and accommodation. Additionally, it should be noted that some national standards were developed based on the national standards of other countries in the world. For example, the State standard Uz DSt 3334:2018 "Tourist services. Muslim hospitality. Requirements" is identical to the Malaysian standard MS 2610:2015 "Muslim friendly hospitality services – Requirements."

For future researchers, it is recommended to focus on studying the national tourism standards of countries leading in terms of tourist arrivals. Based on the information studied, practices used in those countries to ensure a high level of service and customer satisfaction can be identified. By studying foreign experiences, existing national standards in tourism, hospitality, and restaurant business can be significantly improved, thereby enhancing the competitiveness of local tourism enterprises at a global level.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the following recommendations can be made to improve service quality in tourism and enhance national tourism standards:

- Encourage the tourism industry to adopt environmentally friendly and socially responsible methods that minimize the negative impact of tourism on nature and society.
- Invest in higher quality training for tourism professionals. It is recommended to create workforce development programs that include training in high-quality customer service that meets all modern requirements and standards.
- Develop quality control programs that set standards for accommodation, food service, transportation, and other aspects of tourism.
- Encourage local communities to contribute to the development of quality service and improvement of existing standards. Provide people with opportunities to participate in projects, events, and open discussions about industry issues, offering fair compensation for their contributions.
- Create more accessible tourism products and promote accessibility for a wide range of travelers, including those with disabilities and low-income travelers.
- Use modern innovative technologies, such as augmented reality and virtual reality, to enhance visitor experiences while reducing the negative impact of tourism on the environment.

List of references

1. The concept of development of the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025 (Appendix No. 1 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 05.01.2019 No. UP-5611)
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 11.09.2023 No. UP-158
3. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On certification of products and services" dated 12/28/1993 No. 1006-XII

4. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Standardization" dated 12/28/1993, No. 1002-XII
5. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Conformity Assessment" dated 04.10.2013. No. ZRU-3
6. Official website of the International Organization for Standardization - www.iso.org